

Milestone M-WP4.1
**“Deployment of the OH-
EpiCap survey tool in
several European countries
on study cases”**

OHEJP JIP MATRIX – WP4

Responsible Partner: 1-ANSES, 23-UoS

Other contributors: 10-FLI, 13-SSI, 16-INIA,
34-PIWET, 36-INSA

GENERAL INFORMATION

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Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 4 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/> National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/> EFSA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> EEA <input type="checkbox"/> EMA <input type="checkbox"/> FAO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> WHO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OIE <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other international stakeholder(s): as per OHEJP dissemination plan Social Media: as per OHEJP dissemination plan <u>Other recipient(s):</u> n.a.

MILESTONE M-WP4.1

“DEPLOYMENT OF THE OH-EPICAP SURVEY TOOL IN SEVERAL EUROPEAN COUNTRIES ON STUDY CASES”

Summary

The One Health European Joint programme (OHEJP) Joint Integrative Project (JIP) “MATRIX: Connecting dimensions in One-Health surveillance” aims to link existing cross-sectorial One Health programmes in European countries, including animal health, public health and food safety. To advance in the implementation of One Health Surveillance (OHS) in practice, MATRIX values existing resources and creates synergies across sectors. The project proposes practical solutions for European countries that want to advance the implementation of OHS.

Among the different solutions¹ is the OH-EpiCap tool, an interactive, stand-alone tool to evaluate the capacities and capabilities for the OHS for a pathogen of choice. Additionally, the tool allows the benchmarking of surveillance capacities and capabilities for comparison

- With other countries for the same hazard;
- Between specific hazards within one country;
- For the same hazard over time.

The tool addresses the need for evaluating strengths and weaknesses of multi-sectoral surveillance systems and identifying opportunities for further integration. The tool evaluates three dimensions:

- Organization of One Health (formalization, coverage / transdisciplinary, resources, evaluation and resilience);
- One Health in operational activities (data collection / methods sharing; data sharing; data analysis and interpretation; communication);
- Impact of One Health (technical outputs, collaborative added values, immediate and intermediate outcomes, ultimate outcomes).

A tutorial has been created to explain how to use the tool. The tool has been reviewed thanks to manifold contributions from the MATRIX Consortium and experts in One Health and multi-sectoral surveillance, including the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA).

As per June 2022, the OH-EpiCap tool and the questionnaire have been already piloted with:

- Anti-Microbial Resistance (AMR) in Portugal
- AMR in France
- Psittacosis in Denmark
- *Salmonella* in Germany
- *Listeria* and *Salmonella* in the Netherlands.

In the framework of the CoEvalAMR project (<https://coevalamr.fp7-risksur.eu/>), the tool will be applied to AMR surveillance systems in other countries and the tool itself will also be evaluated.

¹ A list of the MATRIX Solution for One health Surveillance is available at: <https://onehealthjep.eu/jip-matrix/>